

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS TRAINING IN WOMEN'S HEALTH PROMOTION

Student of women's sports

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Abstract: In this article, in order to optimize the educational process of "Physical culture" education, the problems of women's sports, women's extensive involvement in scientific activity and a description of the laws of physical activity.

Keywords: women's sports, extensive involvement in scientific activity, physical activity, exercise, healthy mother, healthy child, adaptation, women's entrepreneurship.

Women and girls' extensive involvement in scientific activity, to support their software development based on modern information and communication technologies, innovative and business ideas, inventiveness, rationalization activities¹ is the main goal of our people. Therefore, our main goal is to prepare women and girls for scientific activities and a healthy lifestyle.

On March 1, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev chaired a video selector meeting on issues of support system for women and further strengthening of their position in society.

In the history of our nation, there were many virtuous women who gave birth to such people and inspired them to great deeds, among our grandfathers. Even today, our women are selfless in raising children, in various fields, in their neighborhoods. A number of laws, decrees and decisions have been adopted in recent years in order to ease their burden and ensure their rights and interests.

¹Appendix 3 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-26 dated November 29, 2021 Decree edited by — National Database of Legislative Information, 30.11.2021, No. 06/21/26/1111

In 2021, 2 trillion soums of loans and subsidies were allocated to more than 200,000 projects within the framework of women's entrepreneurship programs, and 320,000 women got permanent jobs. 190,000 women were trained in the profession. More than 4,000 women were allocated funds for the initial housing payment.

2 thousand girls were admitted to higher education on the basis of a separate grant. As a result, 60 percent of students who entered higher educational institutions last year were women.².

In order to fundamentally improve the state management system in the field of physical education and sports, to widely promote a healthy lifestyle among the population, especially among young people, as well as five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 The problems of women's sports are focused on among the tasks defined in the strategy of actions and the concept of administrative reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan.³.

Sports activities: professional (creative) exams of women's sports development educational areas are carried out in the same order as the exams of selected sports.

In the development of women's sports, the activities of educational institutions, family, authorities are being coordinated on the basis of a specific action program. It is to identify our talented women who are interested in sports in the neighborhood and guide them in a promising way. Educational quotas for sports were allocated for women at the faculties of physical culture. The leading scientists and specialists of the world are involved in the process of improving the qualifications of female teachers and coaches in the field of sports.

In particular, according to the results of the research conducted in foreign countries (Russia), the phenotype of intersexuality (masculinity, athleticism) was determined in the majority of female athletes. This phenomenon is reported by 75%

²It was taken from the speech of President Sh.M.Mirziyoyev at the video selector on March 2, 2022.

³"Science and Education" Scientific Journal / ISSN 2181-0842 April 2022 / Volume 3 Issue 4

of non-professional athletes, including 98% of gymnasts, 70-90% of female track and field athletes, 71% of skiers, 67% of soccer players, and 44% of swimmers. observed in female athletes.

And we have physical activity of women is 60-80% of that of men. Performance - as an organism's ability, actually represents the aspects of the athlete's special physical preparation, during the initial study it will be possible to base on the specific details of the special endurance characteristic of cyclical sports.

How about Uzbek women? When the expression "business" found in most sources is used, the thoughts and attitudes that are fundamental in reflecting the essence of some events of this direction are observed scattered. This situation has an undoubted negative impact on the development of separate methodologies, evaluation criteria and standardization of performance parameters for women's and men's sports. It is noted in the scientific reviews that practically all expressions (descriptions) related to this issue contradict the official logic and apply only to certain situations, in most cases instead of the phrase "workmanship" preparation, athlete's condition, Pedagogical phenomena are analyzed through practice phrases Practice (or, fitness with exercise) is a specific state of the organism, which means changes in the parameters of its morphological and functional characteristics under the influence of exercise. The true nature of the definitions of training and physical preparation can be formed only by comparing all the parameters of the athlete's comprehensive medical examination with the indicators representing the functional state of his organism.

Physical education is important in maintaining and strengthening movement activity and health of young people. Therefore, the comprehensive program on physical education should be directed to the all-round development of the growing generation, to strengthening health, and to the growth of students' work ability. At the same time, it should also be mentioned that it is important to pay attention to the development of pedagogic tools, methods and methodological instructions of healthy physical education. In addition, it is necessary to take into account a person's

desire to protect and strengthen his health, the satisfaction he gets from physical training, and his interests. An individual approach to physical education of young people should become the main focus of the pedagogical system.

In order to eliminate the existing problems in Uzbekistan, from the first days of independence, on the initiative of the country's leader, relevant laws, presidential decrees and decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers aimed at the development of physical education and sports were adopted step by step and introduced. In the short term:

- the organizational foundations of physical education and sports management have been improved;

- The National Olympic Committee of Uzbekistan, sports federations were established;

- physical education and health, mass sports activities and national types of sports were developed;

- the system of financing physical education and sports was improved, the non-state sector was developed; The material and technical base of physical education and sports was strengthened;

- training and retraining of personnel in the field of physical education and sports is being carried out according to the national educational program.

Therefore, we young people should take advantage of these opportunities and strive to be perfect in every field. We should contribute to the education of healthy, strong, intelligent and patriotic young people in our society.

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